

Decentering the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Synthesis Report – WP7

Return in Mobile Trajectories

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List of abbreviations

EU – European Union

DGMM – Directorate General of Migration Management

LFIP – Law on Foreigners and International Protection

SNIA – National Immigration and Asylum Strategy

IOM – International Organization for Migration

AVRR – Assisted Voluntary Return and Reintegration Program

NGO – Non-Governmental Organization

LGBTQ+ – Lesbian, Gay, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer (and others)

TP – Temporary Protection

YPG – People's Defense Units

GAPs Project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study on the drivers of return policies and the barriers and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by de-centring the dominant, one-sided understanding of “return policymaking.” To this end, GAPs:

- examine the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance;
- analyse enablers and barriers to international cooperation, and
- explore the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs project combines its decentring approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures, which allows the project to analyse governance fissures;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU Member States and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and
- a trajectory approach that uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs project is an interdisciplinary 3-year project (2023-2026), co-coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies with 17 partners in 12 countries on 4 continents. GAPs' fieldwork has been conducted in 14 countries: Jordan, Lebanon, Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece and Iraq.

This synthesis report has been compiled in the context of the GAPs Work Package on ‘Return Aspirations and Trajectories of Migrants’.

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Executive Summary

This report explores return aspirations and trajectories of migrants by examining the governance of returns and migrants' perspectives and experiences on return from Turkey, Morocco, Poland, and Greece. These countries were selected because they can be seen as transit zones - not just as "transit countries" within migration chains, but also frequently in migrants' own accounts of where they are on a mobility trajectory. The report investigates how these countries' return migration governance influences return dynamics, outlining trends in migration, policy evolution, issues in host societies, and socio-political conditions. Additionally, it highlights migrants' strategic agency in navigating restrictive legal, social, and economic conditions, as well as their experiences in host contexts and their perceptions about further mobility (including return).

Migration Trends and Policy Shifts

Turkey, Greece, Morocco, and Poland's migration governance reflects broader geopolitical shifts in global migration politics. These four countries, positioned at key intersections of international migration pathways, have transitioned from transit states to host countries, adopting diverse approaches to governing migrant returns. Turkey and Morocco, historically considered transit states, now host significant migrant populations, with Turkey accommodating large numbers of Syrian and Afghan migrants and Morocco hosting African and Arab migrants. Greece has been a primary entry point into Europe, particularly since 2015, while Poland has received labour migrants from Ukraine for several years. Migration policy in these countries is shaped by EU pressure, security concerns, and domestic political factors. Notably, nationality-based differential treatment is evident in both Poland and Turkey, where reception and return policies vary depending on migrants' origins and legal statuses.

Return Migration Governance and Agency

Return migration has become central to migration policy across these four countries, influenced by international agreements and domestic political priorities. Policies range from voluntary return programs to forced deportations and pushbacks:

- **Turkey** encourages "voluntary" returns for Syrians amid political pressure while forcibly deporting Afghan migrants and enforcing border pushbacks with Iran.
- **Greece** has intensified pushbacks and forced returns, raising human rights concerns.
- **Morocco** coordinates voluntary return programs with the IOM while selectively deporting certain groups.
- **Poland** maintains a dual approach, sheltering Ukrainian forced migrants (with temporary protection status) while increasing pushbacks at the Belarusian border.

Despite these restrictive policies, migrants exercise significant agency, strategically navigating legal restrictions, economic constraints, and security risks in pursuit of safety and dignity. The threat of deportability does not simply immobilize migrants but generates complex and creative responses, such as onward migration, invisibility strategies and use of social networks. Migrants thus challenge state control over migration, even without formal

opposition. Economic capital remains a decisive factor in determining migrants' agency, with limited legal pathways often forcing them into precarious alternatives.

Barriers to Return Migration

Despite policy efforts encouraging return, multiple structural and individual deterrents prevent migrants from going back. Key barriers include:

- **Security threats:** Fear of persecution, war, forced military recruitment, and repression in origin countries.
- **Economic instability:** Poor job prospects, lack of social services, and exploitative working conditions in countries of origin, lacking infrastructure (in terms of housing, work places) due to hostilities.
- **Informal, unprotected work conditions:** Low wages, exploitation, and unsafe workplaces, exacerbated by rising living costs and financial burdens, creating instability yet not necessarily incentivizing return.
- **Legal insecurity:** Migrants face restrictive, costly, and uncertain legal systems, with permit delays, cancellations, and exploitative conditions. Deportability—through detention, raids, and forced relocations—creates a climate of fear, job insecurity, and psychological distress, shaping economic opportunities and daily decision-making.
- **Psychosocial costs:** Return is often seen as a personal failure after significant financial and emotional investments in migration. This psychological burden, along with uncertainty about reintegration, discourages return.

While some migrants—particularly aging communities in Poland, Greece and Morocco—view return as an option due to family or health needs, most remain in precarious situations, unable to return yet struggling to move forward.

Onward Migration and Return Options

For most migrants, return is not the preferred choice; rather, onward migration remains a strong aspiration. Motivations for secondary migration include:

- **Legal stability and security:** Greater possibilities for naturalization in Western European countries such as Germany and Sweden and clearer policies related to asylum seekers in terms of stability, access to job market and social support systems.
- **Better economic opportunities:** Western Europe is perceived as offering more stability and higher wages.
- **Social exclusion and discrimination:** Migrants facing marginalization in their current host countries often seek more welcoming environments.

However, restrictive migration policies, economic constraints, and the physical dangers of irregular migration significantly hinder onward mobility, often leaving migrants trapped in legal limbo or precarious survival strategies.

One of the main contributions of the report is that it identifies several shared trajectories, even amidst the varying national and social contexts across Greece, Morocco, Poland, and Turkey. These intersecting migration trajectories reveal agentic lives shaped by limitations,

adaptations, and changing aspirations. Across differing policy contexts, these transit states create highly convergent mobility patterns—ranging from trapped and insecure statuses to strategies to settle - urging analysts and policy-makers to move away from rigid, state-centred typologies towards more migrant-centred, situational analyses.

Conclusion

Return policies in Turkey, Greece, Morocco, and Poland are increasingly restrictive, shaped by security concerns, political pressures, and international agreements. Migrants face structural barriers—security threats, economic instability, and legal constraints—preventing return. The psychological burden of return as failure further deters mobility. Parallels between reasons for departure and reluctance to return challenge traditional definitions of return. Future research should examine return in shifting political contexts, the impact of transnational links, and the effectiveness of “go-and-see” policies. Sustainable return policies must address root causes, ensuring voluntariness rather than relying on deterrence, which risks re-migration and policy failure.

Keywords: Return Migration, Governance, Forced and Voluntary Returns, Migration Policy, Onward Migration Aspirations

1. Introduction

While much of the scholarly focus on return migration has been on policy frameworks and state mechanisms, far less attention has been paid to how migrants themselves experience, negotiate, and enact return within broader im/mobility trajectories. To address this gap, this Work Package (WP7) examines return decision-making in transit contexts, centering on the agency of migrants as they consider, plan, and experience mobility. It specifically asks: (i) How do return and readmission policies shape migrant decision-making and lived experiences? (ii) How do migrants' own aspirations, social embeddedness, and previous mobility experiences affect their return journeys?

WP7 contributes to GAPs' broader objective of foregrounding migrant agency and introducing a micro-analytical perspective to return governance. It does so by pursuing three interrelated aims:

- Mapping return trajectories with attention to their fluid and non-linear nature, including onward movements, reorientations, and temporary settlement phases;
- Identifying the influence of diaspora organizations and transnational networks in shaping return processes;
- Examining migrants' agentic strategies in response to shifting legal, social, and economic conditions.

Methodologically, WP7 adopts an ethnographic and sociological approach, conducting fieldwork among diverse migrant groups in transit-host countries, including irregular migrants, settled migrants, and those enrolled in voluntary return programs, as well as individuals subject to forced return procedures. The research follows a multilevel analytical framework:

- At the micro level, it investigates how personal experiences, social networks, and local or transnational media shape knowledge about return and influence decision-making. Particular attention is given to labour market conditions, experiences in transit countries, and gendered dynamics in return planning.
- At the meso level, it explores the role of actors such as diaspora organizations and migrant networks in structuring return processes and influencing mobility decisions.
- At the macro level, WP7 builds on insights from WP2 and WP4 to assess how specific policy frameworks and governance infrastructures shape migrant trajectories, either facilitating return, reinforcing settlement, or compelling onward mobility.

A key aspect of this Work Package is its focus on the interplay between return governance and migration control mechanisms, including pushbacks, readmission agreements, and return infrastructures linked to EU externalization policies. It examines how risks, uncertainty, and coercive practices intersect with migrants' aspirations and strategies. Empirical research was conducted in four key transit-host countries—Greece, Turkey, Poland, and Morocco—providing a comparative perspective on return trajectories across different governance contexts. These countries were specifically chosen for their role as transit zones—not only within broader migration chains but also in shaping migrants' aspirations and perceptions. Beyond their geographic function, they serve as sites where migrants navigate complex and often uncertain futures. The concept of "stuckedness" captures this socio-temporal reality,

reflecting the prolonged limbo that defines many migrants' lived experiences, where movement, settlement, and opportunity remain in constant tension.

This report starts with information on methods used, then proceeds with a section on context where we discuss how we conceptualize 'migrants' and provide an overview of the reasons for migration and the governance of initial arrival and settlement for the case-studies central to this Work Package and report. We then move to our findings, consisting of sections on (1) Agency and movement and (2) Experiences in local context followed by (3) Perceptions about further movement. The report then concludes with some reflections that position our findings in the broader literature on return migration.

2. Methods

The empirical research, started in May 2024 and completed in September 2024, employed a multi-sited qualitative research strategy, incorporating a mix of anthropological and sociological fieldwork techniques across four primary sites of research: Turkey, Morocco, Greece, and Poland. Our strategy sought to highlight the complexity of return migration by interacting with migrants at various stages of decision-making on returning. We include the perspectives of irregular migrants, settled migrants, and participants of voluntary and forced return programs.

The study utilized in-depth life stories and semi-structured interviews of migrants to explore changing aspirations, social embeddedness, and mobility decisions. The interviews were conducted by teams in the four main study sites, and followed stringent, pre-agreed participant recruitment and sampling strategies. They include 30 semi-structured interviews in Greece, 32 in Morocco, 31 in Poland and 42 in Turkey (total: 135).

The Turkish research covered regular and irregular migrants in several cities in the country, including Istanbul, Gaziantep, Van, and Izmir. The majority of participants were Syrian and Afghan nationals, with additional representation of other nationalities from Africa and the Middle East. Gender representation and age variation were considered during the selection, as well as the timing of migration (i.e., earlier and more recent migrants).

In Greece, the research team met with regular and irregular migrants who were from a number of countries, including Pakistan, Georgia, and Albania. The sample included diverse migration histories, with a significant number of the participants having had return experiences and engaging in circular patterns of migration within the EU.

The Moroccan study focused on the country's twin role as a destination and transit country. Irregular as well as regular migrants took part, with the heavy involvement of refugees and asylum seekers. In Morocco the focus was on migration channels that align with Morocco's National Immigration and Asylum Strategy, and thus encompass the experiences of migrants from several West African countries (Senegal, Côte d'Ivoire, Mali, and Guinea).

In Poland, the study concentrated on vulnerable migrants, including asylum-seekers and returnees who are under varying pressures to return. Researchers examined how Belarussian migration is instrumentalized in the country, while maintaining an eye on varying demographic patterns among returnees.

Preparation for the research began with developing fieldwork guidelines and interview templates. All research organizations involved in the study had appropriate ethics approvals

for their context. Preparation was further supported through a workshop that structured the writing of this paper.

Data analysis was iterative with transcription and coding of interviews carried out in accordance with a common framework. Analysis utilized both deductive and inductive strategies so that predetermined themes could be explored while also maintaining flexibility to respond to emergent patterns. Researchers in the four countries communicated regularly so as to ensure methodological coherence and facilitate comparative analysis.

The study examined various aspects of return migration, from individual aspirations and experiences to interactions with readmission mechanisms. It considered the activities of migrant associations and diaspora organizations, as well as how policy regimes influence the experiences of migrants. The qualitative strategy employed in this WP provides rich insight into how return expectations evolve over time, the network and institutional roles involved in return decision-making, and the impact of policy designs on migrants' daily lives. The findings reported here will eventually become part of the final synthesis of the GAPs project, informing comparative studies of return governance.

This synthesis report is based on a comparative analysis of four case studies conducted in diverse and unique national contexts, Turkey (Rottmann et al, 2024), Morocco (Hamdouch et al, 2025), Greece (Papatzani et al, 2025) and Poland (Krepa et al, 2025). Nevertheless, the shared analytical framework—structured around agency and movement, settlement in local context, and perceptions of onward movement—enabled systematic comparison. By synthesizing these case studies, we show both general and country-specific trends, offering a nuanced picture of migration governance and migrant agency.

3. Background of Migration Governance in the Four Countries

Historical migration and reception patterns in Turkey, Morocco, Greece, and Poland reflect trends shaped by the countries' respective geo-political positions, policy contexts, and linkages with neighbouring areas, including the EU. All of these countries have experienced radical shifts in their roles as destination, transit, or sending countries, particularly since the 1990s.

3.1. Shifting Migration Roles

Both Turkey and Morocco have transformed from being predominantly transit countries to host countries, though under different circumstances. Turkey's position as a top migrant-host country arose primarily as a result of the war in Syria that started in 2011, although it also maintained its historical position as a transit/host country for Afghan immigrants since the 1980s (İçduygu and Karadağ, 2018). Morocco's development was more gradual, progressing from a primary emigration country in the 1990s to a transit and destination hub for North, West, and Central African, and Arab, populations in recent years.

Greece became a destination country in the 1990s primarily for Balkan and Eastern European immigrants, mostly from Albania, and subsequently becoming a major entry point to Europe in 2015 during the so-called “refugee crisis”, and eventually a host country again as migrants were placed in camps and sought asylum in the country. Poland, in contrast, remained predominantly an emigration country until quite recently (Matyja, Siewierska-Chmaj, Pędziwiatr 2015; Adamczyk 2021) when it began accepting significant numbers of labour

migrants, primarily from Ukraine (Jaroszewicz, Grzymiski 2021). Until 2015 immigration was a peripheral policy issue.

The convergence of these four countries as new destination countries is striking evidence of the effects of restrictive EU migration policies (externalization) on the one hand and migration pressures from the EU's neighbouring regions (Ukraine-Russia, Middle East and African conflict and economic turmoil) on the other.

3.2. Policy Responses and Legal Frameworks

Migration is governed differently in the four different countries, reflecting their relations with neighbouring countries and international actors.

Turkey's migration policy is strongly shaped by its EU accession process and the EU-Turkey Statement of 2016, shifting from a transit to an immigration country, with the support of the EU. Its policy evolved from an open-door policy toward Syrians (2011-2014) to closed-door policies with an emphasis on returns since 2019. Institutional reforms such as the creation of the Directorate General of Migration Management (DGMM) have consolidated governance. The 2014 Law on Foreigners and International Protection (LFIP) reshaped the governance of migration, with new provisions on work permits, residence permits, and social benefits. Yet, it also brought in inequalities in the treatment of migrants, notably between Syrians and Afghans with Syrians under Temporary Protection having better access to services and institutional support. It must also be mentioned that Turkey's geographical exception to the 1951 Refugee Convention restricts the granting of refugee status to European nationals and thus excludes the migrants that are present in large numbers (Syrians and Afghans, among others) from seeking asylum.

Morocco's migration policy shifted from a security-focused policy in Law 02-03 (2003) to a rights-based policy with the 2013 National Immigration and Asylum Strategy (SNIA). Regularization campaigns in 2014 and 2017 improved migrants' access to services, driven both by local civil society mobilization and Morocco's own migration experiences. European border externalization policies continue to hold sway over its general migration management policies, as Morocco's policy tries to balance EU pressure for increased management of external borders with national strategic interests.

The migration policy of Greece developed from an unstructured system in the 1990s to a system constantly irregularising migrants, even those settled in the country for years (Papatzani et al., 2024). The 2015 "refugee crisis" triggered a significant policy change, combining the EU Hotspot approach with the EU-Turkey Statement to achieve a perceived migration control. Greek policy is deeply embedded in EU institutions, and involves extensive institutional activity, such as Frontex management. After the 2020 Evros border events, Greece positioned itself as Europe's 'shield', by increasing securitization and border control measures, resulting in criticism for human rights violations and controversial detention and push-back practices.

EU membership conditionality and local security dynamics influence Poland's migration policy. Since 2015, Poland has pursued highly securitized asylum policies alongside an open-door policy towards labour migrants, especially for Ukrainians (Łazor 2016). The contradictory nature of the two approaches to policy is apparent in restrictive practices, such as pushbacks along the Belarusian border coupled with temporary protection mechanisms for migrants from Ukraine. Currently, the Polish government attempts to balance EU

membership obligations with neighbourhood geopolitical tensions, particularly towards Russia and Belarus.

Across all four countries, the external pressures on migration governance have produced tensions between security and humanitarian imperatives, resulting in policy incoherence and changing levels of protection for migrants.

3.3. Challenges and social reception in local context

All four countries also face challenges with regard to migrants' reception and settlement in local contexts, but the nature and extent of these issues vary. Syrian migrants in Turkey enjoy Temporary Protection Status that comes with rights to services but barriers to stable lives and the right to free movement, as they predominantly remain constrained from participating in the formal labour market. Afghan immigrants and others are even more disadvantaged as they lack basic legal protections and access to services, in addition to being excluded from the formal labour market.

Morocco's governance policies have shifted over time, but in general, migrants lack access to social services and prospects of longer-term settlement. Public sentiments and attitudes regarding migrants are relatively tolerant in the country compared to the other three countries discussed here, partly due to the presence of Moroccan returnees, which leads to some forms of solidarity.

Greece shares challenges with Turkey and Morocco, compounded by financial factors, particularly after the crisis of 2009, when a significant number of settled migrants (documented and undocumented) departed. Greece's reception system, including camps and urban accommodation programs, has shifted over time, and is usually determined to be failing to provide adequate facilities to asylum seekers.

Poland's context is characterized by a stark contrast between the reception of Ukrainian migrants, who are accorded temporary protection as well as broader social acceptance, when compared to other migrant categories, such as those attempting to enter or entering via the Belarus border.

3.4. Mapping return migration governance systems in four countries

Return migration governance in Turkey, Morocco, Greece, and Poland is shaped by domestic politics, international agreements, and shifting migration patterns. While each country employs distinct return frameworks, all share a trend toward increasing restrictions on stay and greater coercion in return practices. Turkey differentiates return policies based on nationality, with Syrians often subjected to "voluntary" returns under duress (by increasing the push factors or in many cases direct "deportation"), while Afghans face deportation. Morocco participates in Assisted Voluntary Return programs in cooperation with the EU, while allowing other migrants to exist precariously in the country. Greece combines forced returns, voluntary return programs, and aggressive pushbacks, particularly since 2020. Like Turkey, which differentiates based on nationality for Syrians and Afghans, Poland enforces strict pushbacks at the Belarusian border, while offering temporary protection to Ukrainians.

Challenges in return governance for all of these countries include blurred lines between voluntary and forced returns, discrepancies in treatment based on nationality or entry mode,

and contradictions between official policies and informal practices. Security concerns often override humanitarian commitments, as seen in Greece's shift from refugee protections in early periods to restrictive border enforcement and Turkey and Poland's selective approach. Return rates fluctuate due to policy changes and external pressures, with Turkey intensifying Afghan deportations, Morocco maintaining steady AVRR participation, and Poland applying dual strategies.

Furthermore, the three country cases illustrate how public attitudes can drastically change with economic and political circumstances and perceived cultural proximity. Competition over scarce economic resources combined with perceived cultural differences have produced challenges in terms of coexistence in Turkey between the host society and migrants. The spread of xenophobia via social media in particular has had a major impact on policies and political discourses, especially during election times. Tight pressure on public services and resources due to the reception of millions of refugees, and the heavy participation of most migrants in the informal, low-skilled sector has led to tensions in specific segments of the labour market over time. Like Turkey, discourses on longer term settlement in Greece are also fuelled by economic considerations, especially since the 2009 crisis, which left little room for sustainable jobs for migrants. Poland's low unemployment rates since 2017, as well as labour migration policies sanctioned by employers, allow for economic livelihoods, but there is no special assistance for labour migrants (they have access to the general systems similarly to Polish citizens). In the same vein as Turkey and Greece, in Poland, there is growing anti-immigrant rhetoric. In the case of Poland, this rhetoric is directed against Middle Eastern and African immigrants. Ukrainian migrants are more socially accepted because of perceived cultural and linguistic similarity. The most complex case is Morocco. Institutional policies like the National Immigration and Asylum Strategy (SNIA) have attempted to counter discrimination, but the situation of migrants still remains challenging. Members of the public have shown some solidarity towards foreign migrants due to their experience with their own Moroccan returnees. Yet, Morocco has endemic unemployment and poverty that restricts most migrants to vulnerable informal sector jobs, even if vocational training schemes offer some better possibilities.

Access to services differs significantly by country. Turkey's service sector is stretched due to the huge number of migrants requiring health, education, and social care, risking sustainability over the long run. Morocco has advanced well in terms of migrant children's access to education and primary healthcare, but secondary and tertiary health care is difficult for migrants to reach. Greece's reception system has transformed significantly, but generally, it does not provide adequate services for asylum seekers. Benefits and other services in Poland are primarily confined to international protection recipients, with NGOs filling in the gaps, particularly for Ukrainians.

Gender and ethnicity are significant dimensions influencing experiences in all countries. Arab and Afghan men face particular discrimination in Turkey, while women have difficulties learning the language and finding belonging in local communities (Rottmann and Nimer 2021; 2022), due to less access to the labour market and less opportunities for education and professional development. In many cases, they are also more vulnerable to discrimination and restrictive cultural expectations around their roles in society. Forced removal operations are disproportionately implemented against certain nationalities in Greece, and the intersectionality of a variety of identities, e.g., gender and ethnicity, creates compounded risks.

Arab men in Poland are discriminated against in the housing market, whereas migrant women face challenges in the labour market due to childcare responsibilities. In contrast, Ukrainian and Belarusian women have become successful businesswomen, particularly in the field of beauty services. In Greece and Morocco, economic issues particularly burden migrant women, who are typically locked in low-wage domestic labour.

Women in all countries face significant dangers of sexual violence. As Zoe, a 29-year-old migrant from Côte d'Ivoire to Morocco said: "Stay in your country; being a migrant is not easy; I knew many people who drowned trying to go to Europe. I regretted migrating, but I gained from the experience." (Hamdouch et al. 2025, 18). Detention experiences are differentiated by gender in all countries, with women being overrepresented for receiving better treatment, but also facing specific risks for sexual violence. The gendered differential in migration enforcement echoes Leerkes and Broeders' (2010) findings on 'crimmigration' selectivity, where irregular migrant women experience lower deportation risks absent criminal involvement. De Genova (2013) conceptualizes this as the contingent nature of migration enforcement (see also Ambrosini (2015)).

Administrative and legal regimes also present distinctive challenges. Turkey's regime of managing migration combines legal insecurity with economic poverty and social exclusion. Morocco have provided prolonged legal status for migrants, but access to services is hindered by practical barriers. Due to the complicated asylum and reception system in Greece, migrants' presence is irregular for an extended period of time while they wait to become regularized. Migrants in Poland may easily become irregular due to procedural issues, particularly when switching employers.

Migrants are subject to discrimination in their daily lives in all of the studied countries. Syrians and Afghans are viewed as economic and social threats in Turkey. Similarly, urban areas in Greece may emerge as sites of xenophobia and exclusion with discrimination reaching profound depths in workplaces, on public transport, and in other sectors of public space. In Morocco, the National Immigration and Asylum Strategy (SNIA) has put in place policies for regulating discrimination, though issues persist. In Poland, political rhetoric and racist language has fueled intolerance towards migrants, particularly from the Middle East and Africa. The rhetorical link officials have made between terrorism and Muslim migration has justified profound exclusion. Ukrainians' experiences are relatively easier, due to cultural and linguistic affinity (which was shown to be inherently volatile over time in other contexts)—although anti-Ukrainian sentiments are still present.

4. Migrants' Perspectives

In comparing the experiences of migrants at risk of return in these countries, this comparative analysis examines three interlinked dimensions: (1) agency and mobility, (2) local contextual factors, and (3) orientations towards further movement. These analytical themes incorporate temporal dimensions in migration trajectories while enabling us to examine the dynamic relations between structural constraints and individual actions and strategies.

The agency and mobility dimension explores how migrants interpret, navigate and negotiate their opportunities for mobility in terms of the policies that limit them and exert control over their trajectories. The following section examines how migrants perceive the structural environment in-depth—e.g., legal context, access to the labour market, and social networks—and their perception of how this impacts their long-term settlement prospects in host nations. The final dimension assesses how individuals evaluate their future mobility opportunities amid evolving economic conditions, transnational networks, and geopolitical uncertainties.

4.1. Agency and mobility

The study of agency in forced migration examines how individuals actively negotiate structural limitations when making decisions about movement and settlement (Bakewell, 2010; Kuschminder, 2021; Triandafyllidou, 2018; Muller-Funk, Ustubici, and Belloni, 2023; Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou, 2024) as well as their daily lives (Kanal and Rottmann 2021). In this report, we focus on how decision-making processes test the limits of agency, leading to creative actions within severely constraining conditions.

Agency in the Decision to Migrate

The life stories of interviewees across all four countries demonstrate how security risks and economic poverty are deeply intertwined as drivers of migration. In most cases, economic hardship arises from insecurity, while economic deprivation can exacerbate vulnerability to violence and instability. Our findings thus challenge the traditional categorizations of migration motives used by international institutions and often even adopted by academics as highlighted by Crawley, Heaven, & Skleparis, Dimitris (2018). Our findings, instead, reveal migration decision-making as a complex, iterative process where economic, social, political and personal factors dynamically intersect.

In Turkey, the accounts of both Afghans and Syrians show that in their home countries they faced security risks and poverty. They made strategic, active decisions to pursue safer and better lives for their families in spite of risks of violence, discrimination, and structural insecurity in Turkey. Their stories illustrate that simplistic accounts of victimhood are insufficient. For Afghans, the primary drivers for migration were threats from the Taliban, impunity for daily acts of violence, and economic collapse. First-hand information indicates that women, ethnic minorities (like Hazaras), and those associated with international bodies were often specifically targeted by regime forces. Crime was pervasive and often went unpunished. They also faced few employment opportunities and restrictive policies for women's involvement in the economy as well as education drove many to migrate. Syrians reported that they fled due to prolonged war in their home country and pervasive violence. ISIS imposed repressive social and psychological constraints in some regions, forcing

individuals into compliance through intimidation. Their lives eventually became intolerable due to bombing, lack of basic services, and economic collapse. Migrants' accounts show both direct rapid mobility (escape – survival migration) due to security concerns and intentional family decision-making leading to planned migration. Indeed, families play a decisive role in migration decisions and the same can be said for return decisions. Other nationals in Turkey such as Palestinians, Sudanese, and Ethiopians also blamed internal conflict and war for their displacement. Palestinian immigrants described worsening circumstances in Gaza, including bombings and strict sanctions as well as insufficient economic opportunities.

In Turkey, despite migrants' movements being overtly influenced by external forces, their decisions demonstrate significant agency as they skilfully navigate limited choices, demonstrating resilience and resourcefulness. For example, Rashid is a 23 years old Isma'ili Shia from Bamyán, Afghanistan who had finished high school and worked as a tailor in Kabul until the Taliban forced businesses to close in 2021. He had to travel to Turkey through irregular routes in 2020, driven by survival and educational ambitions, first working on farms and in factories. As he explains,

I wanted to move to Turkey regularly with a visa, but when the Taliban took over Afghanistan, I could not get a passport. All the embassies and governmental ministries were shut down. I had to travel irregularly. It took me 40 days to get from Kabul to Istanbul. I paid 2000 dollars. I did not eat or drink for three days during my journey. I came through Iran, and the smuggler dropped us in a desert-like place when we got to Turkey, and there was nothing there. It was very cold.

In Morocco, migrants were more likely to cite economic necessity and poor services in the home country (i.e., lack of access to education) than migrants in Turkey. However, as with Afghans and Syrians in Turkey, security concerns are also main drivers of their decision to migrate. For example, Sasson, a 53-year-old from Nigeria, shared, "My parents are dead, and I was in danger back home," while Moaz, a 20-year-old from Eritrea, explained, "I left my country at 14 because military conscription starts at 15" (Hamdouch et al. 2025, 17).

In Greece, similar to migrants in the other cases, political repression, conflict, and insecurity were also mentioned as reasons to migrate. Unemployment, poor wages, and diminishing economic prospects triggered decisions for some, especially when there was a necessity to support relatives in the home country. Some migrants decided to migrate for family reunification motives, as well as for security and economic reasons. However, our research reveals how bureaucratic barriers - including protracted processing times and cumbersome requirements often transform these migration pathways, and drives migrants into irregular movement channels. Rather than passively experiencing long-term waiting, migrants in Greece actively seek alternative means of moving, instead of complying with official procedures.

Migrants in Poland, also fled security issues, in particular war, violations of human rights, gender-based violence stemming from patriarchal structures, political instability, or ethnic persecution as well as gender-based violence stemming from conservative family norms and structures. Economic reasons were less likely as compared to the narratives of migrants in the other examined countries. In Poland a particularly clear example of using agency is those on

the trajectory of “Planning settlers”. These individuals would extensively do prior research, contact members of their social networks and compile web data on probable destinations beforehand. Their decision-making demonstrated consideration of a variety of parameters, ranging from the strictness and duration of immigration procedures, job and study opportunities to climate considerations. A good case in point showing this agency comes from a migrant to Germany who was in danger of Dublin return to Poland but dodged it by way of “church asylum.” Describing his experience: “But this church which I was there, you had to be Christian. You had to be converted to a Christian. So I accepted, and I said, okay, no problem. I will be, uh, Christian if you assist me, I will remain here. [WP7_14]” Religious conversion is an extreme case, but what this account shows is the way that migrants utilize the opportunities and institutions already in existence to succeed in their aim of migration. By comparison, those who could be considered “spontaneous settlers” in Poland view their mobility as less the product of intention and more the product of circumstance or chance. While at first glance their narratives stress forces outside of their control as determining their choice, even within these narratives, we find moments of decision-making that reveal agency within severely limited options.

When taken together, we see that migrants’ decisions to migrate were situated at the intersection between security needs and economic distress in all countries. While migration is quite literally “forced” in all of the cases, migrants were thoughtful in their reaction to their situations, using all of the means available to them to enhance their circumstances and those of their loved ones. Although we can see agency in every story, migrants also have diverse opportunities for exercising agency: The chosen routes are dependent on the economic situation of individuals highlighting how economic capital translates into the ability to exert agency within movement. Other factors include family-friendly networks and accessibility as people often choose countries that are near borders for example or places that do not require entry visas.

In all countries, the selection of a particular destination is sometimes strategic and thus an indication of agency, however, the constraints of limited and changing legal frameworks compel migrants toward risky alternatives, or towards staying against their will.

4.2. Agency in the Face of Livelihood and Socio-cultural Realities

Overall, our findings highlight the emotional toll of migrants’ precarity as they navigate economic hardship, legal uncertainties, and social challenges, often feeling vulnerable, exploited, and fearful for their future. While social networks provide crucial support, discrimination and limited access to essential services exacerbate their difficulties. Yet, migrants display remarkable resourcefulness in response to systemic barriers and create adaptive strategies that demonstrate agency in spite of exceptionally constraining environments. Similar to Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou’s (2024) work, which highlights migrants’ agency in opposing, challenging, or acquiescing to return processes, our research found a variety of adaptive strategies in play, including informal coping strategies, creative bypass tactics, proactive self-improvement, onward migration, social invisibility practices and use of social networks to achieve their aims.

Confronting a Harsh Economic Situation

Migrants in all four countries face precarious positions in the labour market and employ a variety of strategies to navigate these difficulties while sending remittances to their families whenever possible.

In Turkey, all migrants reported severe economic struggles and are usually unable to meet their living expenses especially in light of recent inflation and rising daily life costs exacerbated after the Covid-19 pandemic period. As most are employed on an informal basis, they faced issues related to lack of job security and social protection. There were many instances in which employers exploited migrants by denying their wages or paying them below the minimum wage, citing economic difficulties as justification. The majority of migrants reported that they worked long hours in difficult conditions. Furthermore, many reported being subject to police crackdowns due to their informal employment status, due to increasing barriers to legal job opportunities (as a result of government policies), which led to living in fear. As with the situation in Morocco and Poland, many migrants in Turkey (and especially Afghans) also have economic obligations towards family members that exacerbate their difficulties. An example of agentic struggle in the face of these economic challenges is Asma and her family. She and her 16-year-old son and 10- and 13-year-old daughters, all work in textile workshops under very harsh conditions. Seven months ago, her husband was deported, because he lacked the necessary papers during a police check. Since then, she was forced to single-handedly look after the whole family.

I go to work every day. I go to work in the morning and come home at 19:30 in the evening and cook for the children. Sometimes when there is a fruit and vegetable market, I collect the leftovers from the sellers and bring them back home for us to eat. I do all the bathing of the children and the cleaning of the house.

People like Asma practice agency through everyday struggles, such as collecting the fruits and vegetables that are headed for the garbage, and finding ways to make an income when unexpected circumstances arise, even if in harsh conditions. They thus resist systematic marginalization through everyday coping strategies.

Migrants working in Morocco face extreme job insecurity. Most participants work in the informal sector and face exploitative unsafe conditions, lacking work contracts and social security. They report struggling to get lasting jobs and many resort to low-paying positions in restaurants, call centres, or as street food sellers. They struggle to make ends meet with their rental and daily living costs placing them in a state of economic vulnerability. Further, many of them send a considerable portion of their earnings to family members in their countries of origin.

Migrants in Greece are also subject to economic precarity, and engaged in undeclared work, particularly if they have irregular status. They are similarly exposed to severe exploitation, including lack of access to healthcare, withheld wages, and insecure working conditions. To navigate these vulnerabilities, some migrants resort to **creative bypass strategies**. For example, some irregular migrants may circumvent labour restrictions by working under borrowed legal documents from other migrants. Such solutions are strategic responses to combat structural exclusion and not simply rule-breaking.

Precarious housing has also fostered innovative solidarity networks among migrants in Greece. More stable migrants retain rental contracts on apartments even when they are not physically present, which they use to provide accommodation to relatives and friends newly arriving. Such practices constitute unofficial safety nets showing collective agency not sanctioned by the state systems. The ability to support families through remittances is a goal, but in some cases is limited given the economic struggles and the precarity of migrants in Greece.

In Poland, migrants reported several issues resulting from their economic situations. The most common difficulty is an inability to work legally during their initial phase of settlement, while awaiting their residence permit which is often delayed due to bureaucratic issues. As a result, many reported relying on economic assistance from relatives living in other countries during this phase. Migrants also struggled with insecure work arrangements or lost their legal status due to employers misunderstanding regulations. On top of that, many are stretched economically due to responsibilities to care for their own families in countries of origin. Women migrants demonstrate significant agency by engaging in **proactive self-improvement**. For example, having recognized language as an obstacle to settlement, they actively seek out and join Polish language classes offered by NGOs. This awareness of pedagogical potential reflects their tactical negotiation of conditions to improve their circumstances in spite of limitations. This example shows that agency is not only exercised in dramatic mobility decisions, but also in the everyday choices to improve one's position given available circumstances.

Facing Legal Challenges and Deportability

Migrants face comparable legal barriers and deportability in all four countries, which they experience as significant sources of insecurity, fear, and exploitation. Members of vulnerable groups, such as LGBTQ+ individuals are disproportionately affected by documentation issues, yet all migrants view asylum procedures as complex and dehumanizing. The outcomes are seen as uncertain, and even temporary status holders feel they have limited protection against changes in their status. Migrants perceive the constant threat of deportation in the four countries as a tool that disciplines their daily lives and decision-making. Enforcement tactics like police "sweep operations," night-time raids, and direct enforcement campaigns create an atmosphere of constant anxiety and restriction of freedom of movement and social networking.

Migrants in Turkey are exposed to a random process of applying for and renewing legal permits. They are often exploited by middlemen who demand high fees. In addition, migrants are affected by successive policy changes which make their future status feel uncertain for an indefinite period of time. Syrian migrants are treated more favourably (with laws towards them being more lenient), while Afghans have to deal with laws that are harsher and consequently more insecurity. The threat of deportation creates a pervasive fear that disciplines daily movement and decision-making. Arbitrary detention and deportation can even be due to administrative errors instead of serious violations. For example, Jamila, 31, from Afghanistan explained, *"To be honest, my life is difficult here. It is like hell for me. I don't have documents here, and I'm afraid every time I go somewhere."* Simple activities become anxiety-ridden: *"I am afraid that the police will catch me every time I leave my home. Last month, there were many police officers here in civilian clothes looking for migrants without IDs."*

As in Turkey, migrants in Morocco encounter obstacles in obtaining and renewing residence permits meaning that their access to services is severely impacted along with their economic security. Migrants also face coercive movement, namely from cities in the north to those in the south. Physical brutality and harassment during interactions with police are the norm. For example, Omar, 30, recounted his experience: “I was arrested by the Auxiliary Forces, sent to Agadir, and after being released, I asked a passerby for 80 DH to buy a bus ticket. I returned to Rabat and decided to go back to Senegal.” His story highlights the cyclical nature of these relocations, which leave migrants stranded, financially drained, and unable to build any form of security even if they return to the initial location of their choice. In Greece, migrants describe highly restrictive residence permit acquisition and renewal policies and having to wait for long periods of time. They are greatly affected by the exorbitant fees and labour requirements, particularly in times of economic recession. They feel dehumanized by asylum procedures. They struggle to reunite with their family due to inflexible economic requirements, resulting in many seeking other, often irregular, means of achieving family reunification. Greece also enacts deportability through police “sweep operations” that create an atmosphere of constant fear, a chronic insecurity. These operations restrict freedom of movement and social networking as migrants attempt to remain inconspicuous. Those arrested frequently experience prolonged detention in police stations or detention centres. The experience of irregularity in Greece significantly shapes migrants’ experiences, where daily interactions between the police and migrants generate feelings of fear and insecurity.

“The first time I got caught, I fell down out of fear. I mean, I passed out, I don't remember anything. And when I opened my eyes, a Georgian woman hits me like this, “Wake up!” she said, “You're all right, they're gone, don't be nervous, everything's fine!”, because I was so scared’ (Salome, from Georgia, 1/5/2024).

In Poland, even when migrants have obtained permits, they do not feel secure as they are often subjected to issues with legislation procedures because their employers do not always sufficiently pay attention to formalities and complex legal frameworks linked to the employment of foreigners. Asylum seekers face very uncertain expectations regarding the results of the application process, and even temporary status holders feel like the protection they have is limited and can be abruptly ended.

Migrants in Poland also face a constant threat of deportation, supported by night-time raids and direct enforcement campaigns, serving as performative deterrence. As in other countries, the impact of deportations is to spread fear among migrant communities. A 42-year-old Chechen who applied for asylum in Poland reported:

At the moment, there is anxiety, worry, anticipation. [...] I feel protected and safe. But the problem is that all this could end tomorrow morning. Tomorrow morning you will receive a refusal, and they can simply come in the morning, take you, put you on a plane and send you home. [WP7_6]

Deportability and documentation status have serious economic impacts on migrants across all contexts, with direct implications in terms of limited labour market opportunities and exploitation through the creation of precarious statuses. The psychological impact of deportation is clear: fear and anxiety. Trauma is also a common consequence of detention, with impacts on family stability and unity.

In each of the national contexts, migrants deploy various strategies to cope with the ever-present threat of deportability. In Poland, the deportation threat compels some migrants to seek **onward migration**. One example is the narrative of an Afghan man who, after detention, migrated to Germany after being counselled by his peers.

When the [Poland's] government doesn't want us, why do I have to stay here? So I moved to Germany and I talked to my friends in Poland. All of them told me that okay, go to Germany. [WP7_14]

Others, like a Chechen woman, state that they are ready to move anywhere to escape forced return.

If there is a threat of deportation of us and my sons, with this threat, I must go to the ends of the earth. I have to protect my children in any way. [WP7_17]

In Greece, migrants resort to **invisibility strategies** and stay away from public areas, restrict their movements, and establish networks to reduce contact with the police. Undocumented residents, such as Tamer from Egypt, account for their ability to avoid arrest due to their proficiency in Greek and their capacity to blend in. In Turkey, increased security pressures lead migrants to limit their mobility. Some even claimed to use employer tips to avoid police raids. For example, Amira's family limits their working days to escape detection,

"We found work at a textile workshop close to our house. There are no checkpoints [MMPs] there... The work isn't daily, just two-three days a week, because we're still afraid of the police."

Fazal, an Afghan migrant, avoids construction sites when foremen anticipate police raids.

"The military is everywhere. If they ask for ID, I don't have one. Sometimes, the foreman tells me not to come, so I don't go to work. The police are reportedly visiting construction sites."

In Morocco, migrants use **social networks for protection**, with men strategically being accompanied by children to reduce their chances of arrest. As Tamutunga explained, he was *mistreated by the Auxiliary Forces*. so, he explained:

"I go out with my roommate's child to avoid being arrested" (51 years old, DRC).

These instances demonstrate how migrants actively navigate hostile migration regimes, employing daily tactics to resist, evade, or reduce the risk of return.

Cumulatively, we see migrants as active agents continuously assessing risks, sharing information through networks, and adapting their behaviour to navigate hostile environments. Each approach - onward migration, invisibility strategies or use of social networks - represents a form of everyday resistance against deportation regimes, that aligns with Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou's (2024) emphasis on migrant agency within return processes.

Accessing services

Migrants perceive access to services in their host countries (Turkey, Morocco, Greece, and Poland) as central to their settlement process but significantly limited and often dependent on their legal status, leading to diverse and often negative experiences. A primary perception

across all four countries is that legal status is the fundamental determinant of access to essential services, particularly healthcare and education. Documented migrants, especially those with refugee status, generally have better experience in joining these systems, while undocumented migrants are systematically excluded or face severe restrictions.

In Turkey, migrants perceive significant variations in healthcare access based on legal status. Syrians with Temporary Protection (TP) have better access compared to Afghan nationals, who, being mostly irregular, are largely excluded. Bureaucratic hurdles, especially without documentation, further complicate seeking healthcare. In Morocco, while primary healthcare may be available in local centres, migrants still face challenges, and they feel very exposed when they become ill and lose work. In Greece, migrants without permission to stay perceive healthcare as starkly restricted, with access often limited to paid services or urgent situations. In Poland, migrants without legal status also perceive limited access to public services and social assistance due to unclear legal provisions, lengthy procedures, and a shortage of qualified staff.

Educational access for migrants varies significantly across the four countries. In Turkey, while Syrians with TP status can theoretically attend public schools and universities, they perceive registration as difficult and limited language support to newcomers including students, whereas irregular Afghans are mostly excluded. In Morocco, migrants' experiences with education are varied, with both successes and ongoing challenges. In Greece, similar to healthcare, migrants perceive the education system as difficult to navigate. In Poland, access to benefits and services, including education, is perceived as primarily confined to international protection recipients, with NGOs often filling in the gaps, particularly for Ukrainians.

Migrants in all four countries lack adequate information about their entitlements and how to navigate the system. They perceive themselves as vulnerable to exploitation when trying to access services, resulting in paying high fees for legal assistance only to receive inadequate support, as for example, reported in Greece.

We found some limited examples demonstrating agency in the face of these constraints. For example, Moldovan-born Larisa, who has lived in Greece since 1999, actively drew on her local social ties to navigate exclusion from the public healthcare system. By cultivating a connection with a neighbourhood nurse, she was able to reach out to a surgeon living nearby and negotiate a discounted cancer operation. Her initiative and use of personal networks allowed her to access essential care that would have otherwise remained out of reach within the private healthcare system.

Her story appears to be the exception rather than the rule. Most examples of agency and resistance strategies are directed against legal categorizations and economic conditions instead of with the aim of accessing services. Migrants in the studied countries perceive access to essential services as largely determined by their legal status so perhaps this is the reason they focus efforts there.

Mobilizing Social Networks

Social support systems and networks are determinant factors that shape migrants' experiences. Ranging from family and ethnic community affiliations to host community and institutional connections, networks shape migrants' ability to cope with problems, access

resources, and create a sense of belonging in their host countries. In the best cases, these relations generate what has been referred to as "urban citizenship," enabling migrants to navigate around systemic obstacles through the relationships they form within and outside of their communities (Vaiou et al., 2007; Zavos, Koutrolikou, and Siatitsa, 2017; Gebhardt, 2016; Bauböck, 2003).

In each country, informal networks are crucial coping strategies where official assistance is not available. Yet, the importance of family ties can vary significantly across contexts and migrant groups. For example, within Turkey, Syrian migrants have more solid social ties due to their larger number and simultaneous arrival times, although some report being rejected by relatives who arrived before they did. They also organize themselves into extended family or tribal groups for mutual support. Afghan migrants report less solidarity among their co-migrants and show greater isolation, with social lives limited to a handful of acquaintances and relatives. Family separation is widespread for migrants in Greece with many leaving their children behind in their country of origin to earn money abroad in support of them, with the plan of eventual family reunification. Having family members who are already established in Greece plays a major role in the decision about whether to migrate in the first place.

In Greece, researchers found that networks are established at various scales and sites of everyday life: between neighbourhoods, during the migration journey, in asylum seeker camps waiting for status determinations, in workplaces, or in urban areas of congregation. For instance, Ali, from Pakistan, who works in local street markets described exchanges of mutual help and care on an everyday basis between himself and elderly people, especially women, in his neighbourhood.

'In the neighbourhood I have 2-3 acquaintances, 2-3 old ladies over there for whom I buy things from here (the street market – 'Laiki') and I carry them for their old man. I hang out with them a bit. Sometimes they send me some candy and look after me, because I live alone and I look after the house too. I leave the house at night and come home at night.... It's a good neighbourhood. They take care of me and I take care of it' (Ali, from Pakistan, 15/4/2024).

In Morocco, migrants form solidarity networks with other migrants strategically as a survival and safety strategy. For example, the team found that migrant men will walk with young children of friends or roommates at night to try to discourage government authorities from picking them up—they rely on observations that men with children are less likely to be arrested. In comparison to networks in the other three countries, Polish and Moroccan migrants reported particularly good relations with the host population and close networks of friends.

Access to formal organizations varies widely across nations. Syrian and Afghan migrants in Turkey reported difficulty in accessing formal support structures, with most not knowing what exists, as access to information on their rights as refugees or to the services they are entitled to remains limited. Moroccan migrants have access to institutional support through international organizations, which provide basic services such as legal assistance and medical treatment to vulnerable migrants or foundations, which provide vocational training and socio-cultural support to facilitate their employment. In Greece, migrants report that migrant support organizations provide essential support with everyday needs, education, social networking, language learning or assistance with legal procedures. They also support migrants

with political activism. In Poland, there appears to be limited contact with official migrant organizations, as migrants mostly utilize informal networks or avoid fellow nationals for fear of political reprisals.

4.3. Perceptions about Future Mobility

Evaluating Return

Overarchingly, no matter how difficult their situation was in the host countries, most migrants felt like return was inconceivable due to on-going security and economic issues, with the psychological impact of returning also playing a role in decision-making for some. The possibility of return is linked to a change in the political-economic circumstances in the origin countries (which led them to migrate in the first place) or the specific conditions of the migrant in terms of life stage, health and economic success.

Migrants in all four countries primarily mention security issues in their countries of origin as the largest obstacle to return (most often the same security issues that drove them to leave in the first place). For example, in interviews in Turkey with Syrians, Afghans, and other migrants all referenced fear of persecution, forced military conscription, and continued violence as reasons that they cannot return. Similarly, Afghans in Greece, cited these same security concerns. Migrants from war zones that reside in Poland discussed political oppression as well as fear of violence as a deterrent of return.

The specific security concerns vary by country of origin: Syrian migrants fear political oppression by different military groups. Afghan migrants are at risk from the Taliban, and face the additional gender-based oppression of women as well as danger if they are LGBTQ+ migrants. Sudanese migrants cite an ongoing war in their country as a barrier to return. Poverty is the second main discouragement to returning. Migrants explained that they would face a lack of essential goods and services, such as bread and electricity, unemployment due to economic collapse or low wages and exploitative working conditions.

The psychological dimension of return is also a burdensome concern, particularly in Morocco, Greece and Poland, and for Afghans in Turkey as migrants may have sold their family's wealth (e.g., cattle) to raise funds to migrate or left behind small children who are dependent on the support coming from abroad. Return would mean defeat and failure.

Despite their general reluctance to return, some migrants indicated that they have considered returning under specific conditions, especially political stability and economic opportunities. Legal status in the host country also influences decisions, with obtaining legal residency being a primary reason for abandoning return plans. Family commitments and aging are also significant yet conditional drivers of return. In Greece, Poland and Morocco, older migrants or those with strong family ties in the origin country find return inevitable as they must care for their aging family members or receive care themselves. Limited healthcare access and deteriorating health in host countries further pushes aging migrants to prepare for return, with many viewing return as the final stage of life.

Considering Onward Mobility

In all four countries, there was a strong drive among interviewees to migrate further when the situation and policies in their transit-host country put them in a tighter spot. The major reasons provided across the board were security and safety concerns, as well as fear of deportation and persecution in their current place of residence. They hoped that moving would lead to better chances of obtaining legal security and rights.

The selection of Europe as a destination is very much shaped by what they hear from acquaintances and previous relatives that have migrated before them. Migrants were especially positive about destinations like Germany and Sweden as they are perceived to offer migrants clearer pathways to citizenship and stronger legal protections and integration policies. As compared to Poland, the asylum process is believed by migrants to be shorter in Germany and the legal status received is more stable, making Germany an attractive destination. Migrants in Greece also claimed to desire migration to Germany because of the possibility of accessing equal rights and citizenship, better employment opportunities and social welfare provisions. Finally, a key reason for choosing a particular country is due to migrants having social networks already settled there.

Among migrants in Morocco and Turkey, economic and educational opportunities also influence migration aspirations. West Africans traveling to Morocco want to pursue work opportunities in Europe and North America, while Syrians and Afghans in Turkey hope to reach Europe for better access to education and social services for their children. Social exclusion and discrimination also play a crucial role in pushing people to migrate further. Racism and social exclusion push Pakistani migrants in Greece to seek new destinations, such as Germany. In Poland, fears of discrimination within migrant co-ethnic groups can also lead to a desire for onward migration. This was the case of a Tajik man who left due to security threats from members of his own community. Despite the risks, interviews reveal a great urge to acquire information about migration opportunities. Migrants' determination to overcome challenges reflects their desire - and agency - to obtain better livelihoods and educational opportunities for themselves and their families.

However, despite strong desires to move, migrants face multiple constraints that hinder their ability to migrate to a third country. Economic barriers are a significant obstacle, as the costs associated with migration—including payments to smugglers and/or legal application expenses—are often prohibitive. Afghan migrants in Turkey and West African migrants in Morocco cite financial hardship as a major constraint. The risks associated with irregular migration further deter movement. While some migrants attempt irregular routes due to restrictive policies, the dangers of injury, detention, and deportation discourage others. When states systematically restrict legal migration pathways – as seen in EU border externalization policies, irregular migration becomes not merely a last resort, but the only viable option for most of the migrants stuck in transit zones.

Legal migration through resettlement is also perceived by most as increasingly difficult due to changing migration policies and tightening asylum regimes. Moreover, even legal migration does not always guarantee security, as migrants in Poland and Greece state that asylum rulings are unpredictable, making onward migration a gamble rather than a guaranteed path to stability. Across all countries, migrants do not mention having received EU's messages of deterrence in the form of information campaigns (Trauner, Brekke, Adam, Cham and

Thorbjørnsrud, 2024). Rather, it is informal community-based sources of information - still indirectly connected to the EU's messages - that deter them from migrating.

Although many migrants want (or wanted) to migrate to a third country, they are not very positive and hopeful about opportunities to do so as the journey itself is risky and costly, and may end in disappointment and eventual forced return. Thus, most are making do in Turkey, Morocco, Greece and Poland, waiting and surviving as best they can.

4.4. Common Migration Trajectories Across the Four Countries

Across Greece, Morocco, Poland, and Turkey, we identified several shared trajectories, even amidst the varying national and social contexts. "Trajectories" refer to patterns of onward movements and re-orientations as well as periods of rest and intermediate forms of settlement (Schapendonk et al. 2021). Examining trajectories facilitates a subject-oriented approach that places migrants' perspectives and their embodied experiences and feelings of movement and stasis as a starting point of analysis (Schapendonk et al, 2020). The patterns we discovered indicate comparable experiences in these "transit countries" and also show diverse levels of agency. The spectrum of agency varies from high constraint levels (trapped, survivalist), mixed (variable levels of agency) to low levels of constraint (strategic and proactive, forward-looking). These trajectories overlap with one another at times and are fluid, but they can also vary with time. For example, migrants can be very optimistic about their future in an early phase of arrival but - and especially in such transit/temporal conditions - can change their aspirations over time. The profiles we portray here are cross-sectional and based on the point in time when interviews were carried out.

Below, we describe the trajectory and the countries in which it was present as well as the specific name given to the trajectory in the reports of the country teams (more information can be found in the specific WP7 Country Reports). Despite the varying names and differing contexts, we were able to find similar patterns of agency and mobility within each trajectory.

"Trapped/Interrupted" Trajectories

This pattern emerges in all four countries, represented by limited agency and disrupted mobility intentions:

- Greece: "Seeking dignity and safety, no hope for return" (Afghan and Syrian migrants)
- Morocco: "The Stagnated Survivor"
- Poland: Circumstances of "Spontaneous nomads" without immediate control over mobility processes
- Turkey: "The Trapped Aspirant"

These migrants usually fled dangerous situations with little planning. They cannot move to target destinations (usually Europe) or return home due to continued dangers. Their agency is thus heavily restricted by legal controls, economic hardship, and safety concerns, leading to a "trapped" condition.

"Circular/Oscillating" Trajectories

This model involves cyclical migration between host and home countries and was present in migrants from all countries except those in Turkey:

- Greece: "Shying away from decades of irregularity, circular trajectories" (Georgian women)
- Morocco: "The Voluntary Return Planner"
- Poland: "Planning nomads" who maintain mobility alternatives with potential return

These migrants possess limited agency within structural constraints. They make strategic choices to move back and forth based on visa regulations, family needs, and economic opportunities. Oscillation is due to both voluntary mobility and forced adherence to restrictive immigration policies.

"Reluctant Settlement/Adaptation" Trajectories

This trajectory is applicable to migrants who initially intended temporary residence in their current host country but end up adapting, a pattern found in all of the countries except Greece. Our teams refer to these trajectories as follows:

- Turkey: "The Reluctant Settler"
- Morocco: "The Optimistic Integrator"
- Poland: "Spontaneous settlers" who stay longer than planned after arrival

These migrants display transforming agency - their initial mobility decisions turn into adaptation strategies as circumstances alter. They form local connections but continue to show ambivalence about settling permanently. Subjectively they display a balance between hope and reality.

"Precarious Survival" Trajectories

This category includes migrants who exist in juridical limbo with survival from day to day being their primary concern. These migrants are also found all the countries except Greece:

- Turkey: "The Precarious Survivor"
- Morocco: "The Stagnated Survivor"
- Poland: "Spontaneous nomads" with no agency over future mobility decisions

These individuals are predominantly "irregular/irregularised migrants" and have very restricted agency, labouring under exploitative conditions with the constant threat of deportation. Their decision-making is survival-focused in the short term and no long-term planning is possible, with their pathways characterized by vulnerability and continuous adaptation to insecurity.

"Forward-Looking/Redirected" Trajectories

This trajectory refers to migrants whose perspective has changed over time as they shifted away from original mobility plans to seek out new destinations. This was a common pattern in all countries except Turkey, where migrants who wanted to migrate further felt overwhelmingly trapped. The teams referred to these trajectories as:

- Greece: "Second generation, looking forward instead of backward"
- Morocco: "The Hopeful Transit Seeker" and "The Risk-Taker"
- Poland: "Planning nomads" who actively maintain mobility options

These migrants exercise agency in directing their trajectories. Second-generation migrants are particularly prominent within this trajectory and show diverging ambitions from their parents'

expectations. For example, they are more likely to consider moving toward Western/Northern Europe instead of back to their parents' home countries if the option arises.

"Integration-Focused" Trajectories

This trajectory was found in all the countries except Greece and refers to migrants actively building lives where they are, which the teams referred to as follows:

- Turkey: "The Aspiring Integrator"
- Morocco: "The Optimistic Integrator"
- Poland: "Planning settlers" who exhibit high agency in choosing their destination and settling on a permanent basis

These migrants exhibit high agency in their own processes of joining the host society, actively learning languages, forming community connections, and strategically navigating legal systems. Poland's "Planning settlers" particularly demonstrate that even those that can be considered "forced migrants" may have high agency in deciding their own trajectory, choosing their destination, and planning when and where to settle on a permanent basis.

The comparative analysis of Greece, Morocco, Poland, and Turkey reveals remarkable similarities in terms of migration trajectories, despite different geopolitical contexts and migration trends. In other words, there are universal patterns of migrant agency and mobility that transcend national divides. The major shared determinants of trajectories include: legal constraints, economic opportunities, security issues, and family imperatives. However, the absence of specific trajectories in certain countries—i.e., "Forward-Looking/Redirected" trajectories in Turkey or "Integration-Focused" trajectories in Greece—shows that there are nevertheless unique structural opportunities and constraints within each national context that can have a significant impact on migrant aspirations.

It is important to note that individuals shift between different patterns of mobility and agency over time. There is a continuum between "strategic" and "trapped" agency, which shows that migrants are not merely passive objects of structural forces but are actively engaging with constraints and opportunities, even when the latter are very restricted. This finding unsettles binary interpretations of voluntary and forced migration, and shows rather, a constant interplay between structure and agency that varies over time. We observe "mixed agency" experiences—whereby migrants make diverse strategic choices even under difficult conditions—suggesting that policy responses must be sensitive to this complexity and diversity of migrants' actions and aspirations.

5. Conclusion

Return policies in all four countries have developed into more restrictive regimes founded upon security imperatives, domestic political pressures, and international agreements. Turkey's policy involves striking differences between Syrians accepted as temporary settlers or returned "voluntarily" (but often forced) and Afghans deported summarily. Greece has accelerated pushbacks and forced returns as part and parcel of EU border securitization. Morocco wields voluntary return instruments through international collaborations, while

managing the pressures of European externalization. Poland implements tough pushbacks on the eastern borders, but has a more lenient attitude towards Ukrainian migrants.

The cases of Turkey, Greece, Morocco, and Poland demonstrate that return migration is influenced by interactions between structural forces and human agency. Security issues arise as the most significant barrier to return across all settings. The majority of migrants consistently report fear of persecution, forced military recruitment, and prevalent violence as drivers for migration and at the same time barriers to return. Such security risks are not vague but rather reflect specific, tangible threats—persecution of minorities, forced military conscription, and political persecution. Return policies need to tackle these underlying security concerns to be sustainable.

Economic collapse in countries of origin intensifies these security threats. Even if physical security could be guaranteed, the absence of employment, essential services, and functioning economies makes return unsustainable. This interdependence of security and economic factors contradicts the institutional separation of "economic return" and "humanitarian return" programs, making more integrated approaches necessary.

The psychological aspect of return is also an important factor to consider. Return is seen by many migrants as evidence of failure and even shameful.

Despite these considerable barriers, our research outlines conditions where voluntary return may be desirable and enabled. Political stability, improved economic conditions, and family responsibilities—especially care for aging relatives—are all important considerations for migrants. The attainment of secure residence tends to undermine ambitions to return, but continued threats of deportability push considerations of further migration or return, despite dangers.

These findings highlight **the tension in return decision-making between agency and structural constraints**. While migrants demonstrate agency in exploring return or onward mobility possibilities, structural barriers limit their capacities to pursue preferred strategies. The result is often involuntary immobility with migrants trapped in conditions with deteriorating circumstances, unable to move.

Across Greece, Morocco, Poland, and Turkey, shared migration trajectories reveal how migrants navigate between alternatives amidst intersecting mobility and immobility constraints. Despite differing policies and geopolitical statuses, these "transit states" produce surprisingly consistent patterns of mobility, including from "trapped" and survivalist trajectories to more strategic ones with a goal to belong. The trajectories approach reveals that migrants' agency is dynamic rather than fixed—predominantly regulated by legal regimes, socio-economic experiences, and social networks—showing variation and uneven practices in mobility profiles rather than reductionist binary categories. As some migrants get stuck in legal limbo or precarious labour market conditions, others shift towards reluctant or hopeful settlement, circular mobility, or redirected futures (particularly second-generation migrants). These findings defy rigid policy models of transit migrants and emphasize the need for overcoming state-based typologies, addressing migrants' own aspirations, adaptations and experiences in diverse contexts.

This report contributes to the literature on return migration by drawing parallels between reasons for departure and unwillingness to return, highlighting the need to revisit the definition of return—return to where? It also challenges conventional push factor frameworks by showing that these models do not translate seamlessly to host country contexts, where—regardless of how difficult conditions become—the prospect of return often remains unviable. This demonstrates the failure of social exclusion policies to achieve their stated aims; instead, they create permanent precarity in host countries. Additionally, this report identifies potential avenues for further research, including the impact of drastic political change in host country contexts on return decisions, particularly in light of recent developments in Syria. Another area for exploration is the role of go-and-see programs or the establishment of transnational links that allow migrants to move back and forth, shaping new forms of mobility and reintegration strategies.

We argue that a successful return migration policy needs to tackle root causes in the origin country and establish conditions of true voluntariness by providing people with circular mobility options. Return policies based on deterrence and enforcement regardless of security and economic considerations will be unsustainable and lead to high levels of re-migration.

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